

Opracował

Mateusz Stachowiak

```
<!-- AWP_In_Variable Name=""RecipeExpInfo".Request' -->
<!-- AWP_In_Variable Name=""RecipeImpInfo".Request' -->
<!-- AWP_In_Variable Name=""RecipeImpInfo".TransferRequest' -->
<!-- AWP_In_Variable Name=""RecipeImpInfo".RecipeIndexToImport' -->
<!-- AWP_In_Variable Name=""Main_DB".StationNumberForRecipeHandling' -->
<html>
<head>
<title>MBranes Config Site</title>
<meta http-equiv="Content-Language" content="en" >
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" >
<meta http-equiv="Content-Script-Type" content="text/javascript" >
<link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="Stylesheet/siemens_Stylesheet.css"/>
<script type="text/javascript">
var StationNumber = 1;
var RecipeSet = 1;
function refreshInputValues(){
StationNumber = ':"Main_DB".StationNumberForRecipeHandling:;
RecipeSet = ':"RecipeImpInfo".RecipeIndexToImport:;
document.getElementById("wert1").value = StationNumber;
document.getElementById("wert2").value = RecipeSet;
}
function setStationNumber(){
StationNumber = document.getElementById("wert1").value;
}
function setRecipeSet(){
RecipeSet = document.getElementById("wert2").value;
}
</script>
</head>
<body onload="refreshInputValues();">
<style>
body
{
background-color: #AAAAAA;
}
</style>
```

```

<!-- Header Line -->
<div id="header">
<table border="0">
<tr>
<td width="300"><h2><big>MBranes Configuration Site </br> Recipes
Handling</big></h2></td>
<td width="450"></td>
</tr>
</table>
</div>
<!-- Header Line End-->
<!-- Navigation -->
<div id="navi">
<ul>
<a href="UserDesktop_Design_from_editor_plus_js.html" style="font-size: 15px;">Stations
Overview</a><br>
</ul>
</ul>
<ul>
<a href="SpeedsSummary.html" style="font-size: 15px;">Speeds summary</a><br>
</ul>
</div>
<!-- Navigation End-->
<!-- Data Area -->
<div id="page">
<h5 style="color:blue">Handling Recipes</h5>
<table width="840" height="30" border=1>
<colgroup>
<col width="280">
<col width="280">
<col width="280">
</colgroup>
<tr>
<form method="post" action="">
<td align="center">
<input type="submit" value="Start Export" style="height: 30px; width: 150px">
<input type="hidden" name=""RecipeExpInfo".Request' value="1">
</td>
</form>
<form method="post" action="">

```

```

<td align="center">
<input type="submit" value="Start Import" style="height: 30px; width: 150px">
<input type="hidden" name=""RecipeImpInfo'.Request' value="1">
</td>
</form>
<form method="post" action="">
<td align="center">
<input type="submit" value="Start Copy" style="height: 30px; width: 150px">
<input type="hidden" name=""RecipeImpInfo'.TransferRequest' size="30" value="1">
</td>
</form>
</tr>
</table>

<h5 style="color:blue">Select Station Number to which You want to import</h5>
<table width="840" border=1>
<colgroup>
<col width="520">
<col width="320">
</colgroup>
<tr>
<form method="post" action="" onsubmit="setStationNumber(); return check();">
<td>
<input type="number" id="wert1" name=""Main_DB".StationNumberForRecipeHandling'
size="2" style="height: 50px; width: 80px; font-size: 15px; text-align: center; padding:
8px;"> Please select Station No. (1 to 4)
<input type="submit" value="Send No." style="height: 30px; width: 120px">
</td>
</form>
<td id="messageId"></td>
</tr>
</table>

<h5 style="color:blue">Select Recipe set</h5>
<table width="840" border=1>
<colgroup>
<col width="520">
<col width="320">
</colgroup>
<tr>
<form method="post" action="" onsubmit="setRecipeSet(); return check();">
<td>

```

<input type="number" id="wert2" name=""RecipeImpInfo".RecipeIndexToImport' size="2" style="height: 50px; width: 80px; font-size: 15px; text-align: center; padding: 8px;"> Please select Recipe set (1 to 10)

<input type="submit" value="Send Recipe set" style="height: 30px; width: 120px">

<input type="hidden" name=""RecipeImpInfo".TransferRequest' size="30" value="1">

</td>

</form>

<td id="messageId"></td>

</tr>

</table>

<h5 id="Smth" style="color:blue"> Current values Recipe set</h5>

<div id="table_distances">

<table width "840px" border="1" align="center">

<colgroup>

<col width="100">

<col width="100">

<col width="100">

<col width="100">

<col width="100">

<col width="100">

</colgroup>

<tr>

<th>Min. dist. <wbr>[cm]</th> <th>Slow down dist. <wbr>[cm]</th> <th>Gap 1
<wbr>[mm]</th> <th>Gap 2 <wbr>[mm]</th> <th>Gap 3 <wbr>[mm]</th> <th>Gap 4
<wbr>[mm]</th><th>Temperature <wbr>down <wbr>°C</th><th>Temperature
<wbr>up <wbr>°C</th>

</tr>

<tr id="gaps">

<td><div id="MinDist">dist_min</div></td> <td><div
id="SlowDownDist">dist_slow_down</div></td> <td><div
id="Gap1Dist">G1</div></td> <td><div id="Gap2Dist">G2</div></td> <td><div
id="Gap3Dist">G3</div></td> <td><div id="Gap4Dist">G4</div></td><td><div
id="Temp_down">T <wbr>down</div></td> <td><div id="Temp_up">T
<wbr>Up</div></td>

</tr>

</table>

</div>

<div id="table_times" align="center">

<table width "840px" border="1">

<colgroup>

<col width="100">

<col width="100">

<col width="100">

```

<col width="100">
<col width="100">
<col width="100">
</colgroup>
<tr>
<th> Cycle No.</th> <th>Pi <wbr>[ms]</th> <th>Ui <wbr>[ms]</th> <th>Slow Pi</th>
<th>Slow Ui</th> <th>Gap No.</th>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl1">
<td>1</td> <td><div id="Pi1">Pi1</div></td> <td><div id="Ui1">Ui1</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi1">SPi1</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi1">SUi1</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no1">Gap No.1</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl2">
<td>2</td> <td><div id="Pi2">Pi2</div></td> <td><div id="Ui2">Ui2</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi2">SPi2</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi2">SUi2</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no2">Gap No.2</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl3">
<td>3</td> <td><div id="Pi3">Pi3</div></td> <td><div id="Ui3">Ui3</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi3">SPi3</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi3">SUi3</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no3">Gap No.3</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl4">
<td>4</td> <td><div id="Pi4">Pi4</div></td> <td><div id="Ui4">Ui4</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi4">SPi4</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi4">SUi4</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no4">Gap No.4</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl5">
<td>5</td> <td><div id="Pi5">Pi5</div></td> <td><div id="Ui5">Ui5</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi5">SPi5</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi5">SUi5</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no5">Gap No.5</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl6">
<td>6</td> <td><div id="Pi6">Pi6</div></td> <td><div id="Ui6">Ui6</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi6">SPi6</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi6">SUi6</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no6">Gap No.6</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl7">
<td>7</td> <td><div id="Pi7">Pi7</div></td> <td><div id="Ui7">Ui7</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi7">SPi7</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi7">SUi7</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no7">Gap No.7</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl8">

```

```
<td>8</td> <td><div id="Pi8">Pi8</div></td> <td><div id="Ui8">Ui8</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi8">SPi8</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi8">SUi8</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no8">Gap No.8</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl9">
<td>9</td> <td><div id="Pi9">Pi9</div></td> <td><div id="Ui9">Ui9</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi9">SPi9</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi9">SUi9</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no9">Gap No.9</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl10">
<td>10</td> <td><div id="Pi10">Pi10</div></td> <td><div id="Ui10">Ui10</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi10">SPi10</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi10">SUi10</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no10">Gap No.10</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl11">
<td>11</td> <td><div id="Pi11">Pi11</div></td> <td><div id="Ui11">Ui11</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi11">SPi11</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi11">SUi11</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no11">Gap No.11</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl12">
<td>12</td> <td><div id="Pi12">Pi12</div></td> <td><div id="Ui12">Ui12</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi12">SPi12</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi12">SUi12</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no12">Gap No.12</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl13">
<td>13</td> <td><div id="Pi13">Pi13</div></td> <td><div id="Ui13">Ui13</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi13">SPi13</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi13">SUi13</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no13">Gap No.13</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl14">
<td>14</td> <td><div id="Pi14">Pi14</div></td> <td><div id="Ui14">Ui14</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi14">SPi14</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi14">SUi14</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no14">Gap No.14</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl15">
<td>15</td> <td><div id="Pi15">Pi15</div></td> <td><div id="Ui15">Ui15</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi15">SPi15</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi15">SUi15</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no15">Gap No.15</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl16">
<td>16</td> <td><div id="Pi16">Pi16</div></td> <td><div id="Ui16">Ui16</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi16">SPi16</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi16">SUi16</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no16">Gap No.16</div></td>
</tr>
```

```
<tr id="cycl17">
<td>17</td> <td><div id="Pi17">Pi17</div></td> <td><div id="Ui17">Ui17</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi17">SPi17</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi17">SUi17</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no17">Gap No.17</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl18">
<td>18</td> <td><div id="Pi18">Pi18</div></td> <td><div id="Ui18">Ui18</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi18">SPi18</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi18">SUi18</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no18">Gap No.18</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl19">
<td>19</td> <td><div id="Pi19">Pi19</div></td> <td><div id="Ui19">Ui19</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi19">SPi19</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi19">SUi19</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no19">Gap No.19</div></td>
</tr>
<tr id="cycl20">
<td>20</td> <td><div id="Pi20">Pi20</div></td> <td><div id="Ui20">Ui20</div></td>
<td><div id="SlowPi20">SPi20</div></td> <td><div id="SlowUi20">SUi20</div></td>
<td><div id="Gap_no20">Gap No.20</div></td>
</tr>
</table>
</div>
<!-- Data Area End-->
<iframe src="Update\_Start.html" style="display:none;" />
</div>
</body>
</html>
```

Handling Recipes

Start Export

Start Import

Start Copy

Select Station Number to which You want to import

Please select Station No. (1 to 4)

Send No.

Select Recipe set

Please select Recipe set (1 to 10)

Send Recipe set

Current values Recipe set

Min. dist. [cm]	Slow down dist. [cm]	Gap 1 [mm]	Gap 2 [mm]	Gap 3 [mm]	Gap 4 [mm]	Temperature down °C	Temperature up °C
dist_min	dist_slow_down	G1	G2	G3	G4	T down	T Up
		Cycle No.	Pi [ms]	Ui [ms]	Slow Pi	Slow Ui	Gap No.
		1	Pi1	Ui1	SPi1	SUi1	Gap No.1
		2	Pi2	Ui2	SPi2	SUi2	Gap No.2
		3	Pi3	Ui3	SPi3	SUi3	Gap No.3
		4	Pi4	Ui4	SPi4	SUi4	Gap No.4
		5	Pi5	Ui5	SPi5	SUi5	Gap No.5
		6	Pi6	Ui6	SPi6	SUi6	Gap No.6
		7	Pi7	Ui7	SPi7	SUi7	Gap No.7
		8	Pi8	Ui8	SPi8	SUi8	Gap No.8
		9	Pi9	Ui9	SPi9	SUi9	Gap No.9
		10	Pi10	Ui10	SPi10	SUi10	Gap No.10
		11	Pi11	Ui11	SPi11	SUi11	Gap No.11
		12	Pi12	Ui12	SPi12	SUi12	Gap No.12
		13	Pi13	Ui13	SPi13	SUi13	Gap No.13
		14	Pi14	Ui14	SPi14	SUi14	Gap No.14
		15	Pi15	Ui15	SPi15	SUi15	Gap No.15
		16	Pi16	Ui16	SPi16	SUi16	Gap No.16
		17	Pi17	Ui17	SPi17	SUi17	Gap No.17
		18	Pi18	Ui18	SPi18	SUi18	Gap No.18
		19	Pi19	Ui19	SPi19	SUi19	Gap No.19
		20	Pi20	Ui20	SPi20	SUi20	Gap No.20

Powyższa ilustracja pokazuje wizualną wersję strony widocznej dla użytkownika wraz z tabelą aktualnie wczytanych nastaw procesu produkcyjnego.

Kolejne strony zawierają stronę HTML wraz z kodem JavaScript, który umożliwia aktualizację wartości poszczególnych elementów w tabeli widocznej dla użytkownika.

```

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC>

<html>

  <head>

<meta content="text/html; charset=UTF-8" http-equiv="content-type" />

  <title>Web page demo - Automatic update - Update page</title>

  <script type="text/javascript">

      var tag_end = "]:"

      /* String.trim() is not supported by every browser - thus add this
      functionality is necessary */

      if (!String.trim)

          {

              String.prototype.trim = function () { return
this.replace(/^\s|\u00A0)+|(\s|\u00A0)+$/g, ""); };

          }

      /* Main function for calling the subroutines */

      function mainJavaScript()

          {

              updateSingleVariablesTable();

              updateFrame();

          }

      /* Function for updating the variables */

      function updateSingleVariablesTable()

          {

var table = document.getElementById("singleVariablesTable");

              var tagValue;

              var tagId;

              for(i = 1; i < table.rows.length; i++)

                  {

```

```

                tagValue =
table.rows[i].getElementsByTagName("td")[0].innerHTML;
                tagId =
table.rows[i].getElementsByTagName("td")[1].innerHTML.trim();
                parent.document.getElementById(tagId).innerHTML =
tagValue;
            }
        }

```

```

/* Function for updating the web page */

```

```

        function updateFrame()
        {
            window.setTimeout(function(){location.reload()},
document.getElementById("updateInterval").innerHTML.trim());
        }
    </script>

```

```

</head>

```

```

<body onload="mainJavaScript()">

```

```

<table border="1">

```

```

    <tr>

```

```

        <td>

```

```

            Update time in milliseconds

```

```

        </td>

```

```

    </tr>

```

```

    <tr>

```

```

        <td id="updateInterval">

```

```

            4000

```

```

        </td>

```

```

    </tr>

```

```

</table>

```


<table id="singleVariablesTable" border="1">

<tr>

<td>

AWP-Command to read variable

</td>

<td>

ID of the element of the main page which should be updated

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[0]:"

</td>

<td>

Pi1

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[1]:"

</td>

<td>

Pi2

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[2]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Pi3
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>
```

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[3]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Pi4
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>
```

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[4]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Pi5
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>
```

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[5]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Pi6
```

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[6]:"

</td>

<td>

Pi7

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[7]:"

</td>

<td>

Pi8

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[8]:"

</td>

<td>

Pi9

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[9]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Pi10
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>
```

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[10]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Pi11
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>
```

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[11]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Pi12
</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>
```

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[12]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Pi13
```

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[13]:"

</td>

<td>

Pi14

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[14]:"

</td>

<td>

Pi15

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[15]:"

</td>

<td>

Pi16

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[16]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Pi17
</td>
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
<td>
```

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[17]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Pi18
</td>
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
<td>
```

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[18]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Pi19
</td>
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
<td>
```

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[19]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Pi20
```

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[0]:"

</td>

<td>

Ui1

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[1]:"

</td>

<td>

Ui2

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[2]:"

</td>

<td>

Ui3

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[3]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Ui4
</td>
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
<td>
```

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[4]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Ui5
</td>
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
<td>
```

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[5]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Ui6
</td>
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
<td>
```

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[6]:"

```
</td>
<td>
    Ui7
```

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[7]:"

</td>

<td>

Ui8

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[8]:"

</td>

<td>

Ui9

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[9]:"

</td>

<td>

Ui10

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[10]:"

</td>

<td>

Ui11

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[11]:"

</td>

<td>

Ui12

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[12]:"

</td>

<td>

Ui13

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[13]:"

</td>

<td>

Ui14

</td>

</tr>

<tr>

<td>

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Ui15

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Ui16

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Ui20

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SlowPi1

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SlowPi2

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SlowPi3

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SlowPi4

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":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.SlowPressing[4]:"

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SlowPi9

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SlowPi10

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SlowPi11

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SlowPi12

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SlowPi13

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SlowPi14

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SlowPi15

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":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.SlowPressing[18]:"

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SlowPi19

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SlowPi20

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SlowUi1

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SlowUi2

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":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.SlowUnpressing[8]:"

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SlowUi9

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":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.SlowUnpressing[9]:"

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SlowUi10

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":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.SlowUnpressing[10]:"

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SlowUi11

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SlowUi12

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SlowUi19

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SlowUi20

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Gap_no1

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Gap_no15

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Gap_no16

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Gap_no17

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Gap_no18

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Gap_no19

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Gap4Dist

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":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.Distances[5]:"

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SlowDownDist

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Temp_down

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":="Main_DB".StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PID_Temp_Up:"

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Temp_up

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</html>

Update time in milliseconds
4000

AWP-Command to read variable	ID of the element of the main page which should be updated
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[0]:"	Pi1
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[1]:"	Pi2
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[2]:"	Pi3
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[3]:"	Pi4
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[4]:"	Pi5
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[5]:"	Pi6
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[6]:"	Pi7
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[7]:"	Pi8
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[8]:"	Pi9
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[9]:"	Pi10
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[10]:"	Pi11
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[11]:"	Pi12
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[12]:"	Pi13
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[13]:"	Pi14
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[14]:"	Pi15
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[15]:"	Pi16
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[16]:"	Pi17
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[17]:"	Pi18
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[18]:"	Pi19
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[19]:"	Pi20
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[0]:"	Ui1
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[1]:"	Ui2
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[2]:"	Ui3
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[3]:"	Ui4
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[4]:"	Ui5
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[5]:"	Ui6
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[6]:"	Ui7
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[7]:"	Ui8
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[8]:"	Ui9
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[9]:"	Ui10
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[10]:"	Ui11
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[11]:"	Ui12
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[12]:"	Ui13
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[13]:"	Ui14
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":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[17]:"	Ui18
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[18]:"	Ui19
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[19]:"	Ui20
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.SlowPressing[0]:"	SlowPi1
":-="Main_DB". StationForHtmlTransfer.ActiveRecipeData.SlowPressing[1]:"	SlowPi2

Powyższy zrzut ekranu pokazuje niewidoczną dla użytkownika stronę HTML, która ułatwia odczyt danych ze sterownika PLC i ich przekazanie do tabeli widocznej dla użytkownika. Takie podejście pozwala na zmianę wartości w docelowej tabeli z wykorzystaniem kodu JavaScript. Pozwala to skrócić i usystematyzować kod HTML, który i tak jest dość pokaźny w swojej objętości.